

A REVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF VISION 2020 UMURENGE PROGRAM ON WOMEN'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE RUSIGA SECTOR, RULINDO DISTRICT, RWANDA

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Abstract:

The Vision 2020 Umurenge Program is one of three flagship programs of the National Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy aimed to eradicate extreme poverty by 2020. An interim target of the program is to lower extreme poverty from 36.9% (2006) to 24% by 2012. Rwanda introduced a comprehensive social protection system in 2016 that tackles multi-dimensional poverty and deprivation at the outset by adapting a defined minimum package which combines both core and complementary social protection programs that aim to enhance beneficiary sustained graduation out of poverty. The study reviewed the impact of Vision 2020 Umurenge Program to socio-economic development of Women in Rusiga Sector. The descriptive, and correlation research designs were applied in this study, while target population was 171 females benefited from VUP program in Rusiga sector. The sample size was 120 respondents, and correlation coefficient and linear regression analysis used to assess relationship between the study variables. The findings revealed that there is a positive and strong correlation between VUP Public works and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District as Pearson correlation is .631**; positive and strong correlation between VUP Direct Support and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District correlation is .551** ; VUP Direct support and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District, and the positive and strong correlation between VUP financial services and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District as indicated by Pearson correlation of .521** with the p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. Based to the findings, all null hypotheses were rejected, and alternative hypotheses were retained which stated that Vision 2020 Umurenge Program (VUP financial services, VUP direct support, VUP public works) have significant impact on socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District.

Key Words: Vision 2020 Umurenge Program, Socio-Economic, Development

Introduction:

In sub-Saharan Africa, development assistance has consequently become inextricably linked to the elaboration of internationally-accepted poverty reduction strategies which also addresses the social and environmental concerns laid out in the MDGs. The internal development policies of many of the poorest countries mirror this 'global' poverty reduction agenda, particularly where dependency on external resources is high. Rwanda is a landlocked country facing rapid population growth. In that regard, the government of Rwanda has developed a road map for sustainable development aiming at attaining the status of middle-income countries by the year 2020. To achieve this ambitious goal the government of Rwanda has developed numerous programs to this effect.

Rwandan society is characterized by a patriarchal social structure that underlies the unequal social power relations between men and women, boys and girls. This has translated into men's dominance and women's subordination. Gender inequalities have not been seen as unjust, but as respected social normality. In the colonial era, men's supremacy over women was reinforced. For example, the abrupt shift from a subsistence economy to monetary economy based on paid employment and a formal education system, weakened women's position relative to that of men. In particular, it weakened their bargaining position on matters concerning their access to and control over resources and the degree of their level of participation in the development process. (MIGEPROF, 2010).

Despite success achieved by the program, the graduation approach for VUP household beneficiaries remains a challenge. In 2016, Rwanda introduced a comprehensive social protection system that tackles multi-dimensional poverty and deprivation at the outset by adapting a defined minimum package which combines both core and complementary social protection programs that aim to enhance beneficiary sustained graduation out of

poverty. However, the minimum package is still under piloting in a few selected districts across the country for future roll out. Moreover, previous studies paid less attention on the improvement of women through VUP. This study aims at bridging this gap since it focused on impact of VUP program to socio-economic development of women beneficiaries. Rwanda perceives social protection as a fundamental topic of importance in line with its development goal of eliminating poverty by 2020.

Objectives of the Study:

The study reviewed the impact of Vision 2020 Umurenge Program to socio-economic development of Women in Rusiga Sector. The specific objectives of the research are as following:

- To evaluate the contribution of public works on women's socio-economic development
- To assess the impact of VUP direct support on women's socio-economic development in Rusiga sector
- To determine the effect of financial services on women's socio-economic development

Research Hypotheses:

This study verified two categories of research hypothesis include a null and alternative hypothesis.

- H0: there are no significant impacts of Vision 2020 Umurenge Program (public works; VUP direct support; and financial services) on socio-economic development of Women in Rusiga Sector.
- H1: Vision 2020 Umurenge Program represented by public works; VUP direct support; and financial services have significant impact on socio-economic development of Women in Rusiga Sector

The Concept of Socio-Economic Development:

Socio-economic development is a wider aspect of society or simply economic development. Whereas economic growth is the quantitative increase in the amount of goods and services in a country, economic development is a both quantitative and qualitative increase in these (Todaro & Smith, 2006). Economic growth is not enough in itself to improve the quality of life but also other factors such as happiness, social needs and the environment which is a consideration in sustainable development policies (Frank & Bernanke, 2012).

Social Development:

Social development is the bundle of technological, subsistence, organizational, and cultural accomplishments through which people feed, clothe, house, and reproduce themselves, explain the world around them, resolve disputes within their communities, extend their power at the expense of other communities, and defend themselves against others' attempts to extend power (Morris, 2010). According to Bilance (1997) Social Development is the promotion of a sustainable society that is worthy of human dignity by empowering marginalized groups, women and men, to undertake their own development, to improve their social and economic position and to acquire their rightful place in society. Socio-economic development is the process of social and economic development in a society.

Economic Development:

According to International Economic Development Center (IEDC), there is no single definition incorporates all of the different strands of economic development. Typically, economic development can be described in terms of objectives. These are most commonly described as the creation of jobs and wealth, and the improvement of quality of life. Economic development can also be described as a process that influences growth and restructuring of an economy to enhance the economic well-being of a community. Economic development is the sustained, concerted actions of policy makers and communities that promote the standard of living and economic health of a specific area.

Social Economic Development Indicators:

Education: there is a strong relation between education level and sustainable development. The developing economy and social life need sufficient number of educated and qualified labor force. In Rwanda, the lack of qualified labor force is always a problem. The low ratio of school enrolment from primary to higher education, the gender inequality problem in school enrolment, lack of educational facilities and personnel are the main problems existing for a long time period (Reed, 2003).

Job creation: Nikkahah et al. (2010) hold positive that. NGOs in Nigeria have created jobs opportunities in communities through the use of both micro finances and capacity building programme. Thus, as the results of job created people are enabled to develop on their selves the thing which leads to their sustainable development.

Health: The level of health services is directly proportional to the level of social and economic development of a region. The increase in the number of health personnel means development as the tendency of such personnel in choosing a work place is usually towards to developed settlement centers. Infant mortality and child mortality rates are related to development of health services, educational and cultural as well as other socio-economic factors (Reed, 2003)

Vision 2020 Umurenge Program (VUP):

Rwanda Vision 2020 is a vision statement for the country's development. It presents the key priorities and pillars to serve as a guiding tool for the future of the nation. It supports a clear Rwandan identity, whilst showing ambition and imagination in overcoming poverty and division. The Government of Rwandan (GoR),

together with its partners, donors, civil society organizations and the private sector, are all committed to make significant headways towards the objectives contained in the national vision.

The VUP builds on past experiences which show that isolated interventions by sector ministries, donors or NGOs are not sufficient to lift people out of extreme poverty in a cost-effective and sustainable fashion. The other extreme, integrated development, has also shown its limits in many circumstances. One of the main limitations of both isolated and integrated approaches has been the failure to address two of the most important insights of economics: (i) resources are scarce and (ii) people respond to incentives. Because resources are scarce compared to people’s needs, choices must be made.

Theory of Change:

Theory of Change is essentially a comprehensive description and illustration of how and why a desired change is expected to happen in a particular context. It is focused in particular on mapping out or “filling in” what has been described as the “missing middle” between what a program or change initiative does (its activities or interventions) and how these lead to desired goals being achieved (Funnell, Sue C. and Patricia J. Rogers, 2011). The Outcomes Framework then provides the basis for identifying what type of activity or intervention will lead to the outcomes identified as preconditions for achieving the long-term goal. Through this approach, the precise link between activities and the achievement of the long-term goals are more fully understood. This leads to better planning, in that activities are linked to a detailed understanding of how change actually happens. It also leads to better evaluation, as it is possible to measure progress towards the achievement of longer-term goals that goes beyond the identification of program outputs, (Taplin, Dana, Heléne Clark, Eoin Collins and David L. Colby , 2013). As theory of Change describe how and why a desired change is expected to happen; also, the aim of VUP is to provide social assistance to the neediest while supporting the able-bodied to graduate from extreme vulnerability and poverty into more sustainable lead to self-support.

Empowerment Theory to Community Development:

According to Ledwith (2005), Empowerment is not an alternative solution to the redistribution of unequally divided resources. Empowerment is more than providing the resources for one to help community out of poverty and hence to earn development, it is the act of providing the necessary tools to shape the whole person and promote a critical way of thinking and consciousness that end up to sustainable community development. Moreover, empowerment is a construct that links individuals’ strengths and competences, natural helping system and proactive behavior to social changes.

Marco (2013) put that, Empowerment theory is based on the explanations of the existing structural inequalities, imbalances, marginalization and oppression. It is guided by the thinking on the relationship between supremacy and poverty shaped by the explanation of tackling poverty and underdevelopment around the world. It offers to empower people in the community that lack access to resources which would enable them to compete more effective in struggle to sustain livelihood community development. Empowerment theory provides and narrates the theoretical argument on the strength of empowerment on sustainable community development, empowerment of the rural community increases the capabilities of the poor to influence and hold accountable the institutions that provided for them. To this end, empowerment attempts to give power and knowledge to rural communities and assisting them in creating better quality of life, so that in the future they have skills and ability to develop on their own “self-reliance” which brought less dependency on external sources to provide vital services and infrastructure (Livingstone 2006).

Conceptual Framework:

According to educational researcher Smyth (2009), concept frameworks are structured from a set of broad ideas and theories that help researcher to properly identify the problem he/she is looking at, frame their questions and find suitable literature. Most academic research uses a conceptual framework at outset because it helps the researcher to clarify his research question and objective

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher Compilation (2021)

Research Design and Methodology:

The study is non-experimental study, for that, it applied descriptive, and correlation research designs. This design is indeed helpful in describing the impact of VUP on women’s social economic development in Rusiga sector. The design is time saving and less expensive compared to other methods and that it offered in depth and breadth analysis of variables under study. It offered flexible methods in data collection and it could be used in conjunction with other designs. The population of the study was 171 females who benefited of VUP program in Rusiga sector. The units of analysis which was used include women who benefited from VUP program.

The study deals with 3 cells in Rusiga which are, Kirenge, Taba and Gako and six villages was chosen in this area namely Kigarama, Kinini, Rebero, Karambi, Kabuye and Rwintare villages. To compute the sample size, the formula of Yamane (1964:886) was used: The formula is $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$; Where: n is the sample size, N is the population size, e specifies the desired level of precision, where precision $e = 1 - \text{precision}$, $p = 0.95$. N is equal to 171, $e(\text{margin of error}) = 1 - 0.95 = 0.05$. $n = \frac{171}{1 + 171(0.05)^2} = 120$. The total numbers of 120 respondents were selected from these villages. Table below shows respondents’ distribution after survey in six villages as the sample response show that the all sample designed were reached and participating during data collection. The closed ended questionnaire was prepared in form of the multiple choices, whereby respondent was asked to put a tick against the answer that was correct. Descriptive and quantitative methods of data analysis were applied in this study. Calculation of descriptive statistics like frequencies, and percentages of some the critical variables were analyzed by using computer statistical package for social science (SPSS) which managed the data too. The study used the correlation coefficient tests and linear regression test to determine the relationship between the variables under study.

Data Analysis and Findings:

A correlation matrix shows correlation coefficients between variables. Each cell in the table shows the correlation between two variables. It is used to summarize data, as input into a more advanced analysis, and as a diagnostic for advanced analyses. Table 1 showed the findings on the correlation matrix test of this study between variables of effective analysis of financial statements as independent variable and financial performance as dependent variable.

Table 1: Correlation coefficient results

		VUP Public works	VUP Direct Support	VUP Financial Services	Socio-Economic Development
VUP Public works	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	120			
VUP Direct Support	Pearson Correlation	.566**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	120	120		
VUP Financial Services	Pearson Correlation	.747**	.495**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	120	120	120	
Socio-Economic Development	Pearson Correlation	.631**	.551**	.521**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	120	120	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The findings indicated that there is positive and strong correlation between VUP Public works and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District as Pearson correlation is .631** with p-value of .000 less than standard significance level of 0.01. This is an indicator of existence of significant relationship between public works in VUP and Socio-Economic Development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. The results show a positive and strong correlation between VUP Direct Support and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District correlation is .551** with p-value of 0.000, less than standard significance level of 0.01 is an indicator of relationship between VUP Direct support and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. The results also indicated positive and strong correlation between VUP financial services and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District as indicated by Pearson correlation of .521** with the p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. The multiple regression models were formulated to review vision 2020 Umurenge program on each indicator of socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District itself. The models are $X = \text{independent variable} = \text{vision 2020 Umurenge program}$, which has three indicators: public works; VUP direct support and financial services while $Y = \text{dependent variable} = \text{socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District}$. $Y = f(X)$; therefore, $y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ functions. However, study verified research hypothesis using findings from linear regression analysis.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.675 ^a	.456	.442	2.30300

a. Predictors: (Constant), VUP financial services, VUP Direct Support, VUP Public works

The results in table 2 showed R=.675a which is positive, significant and strong relationship between Vision 2020 Umurenge Program represented by VUP financial services, VUP Direct Support, VUP Public works and socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. R² or R-squared (R²) is a statistical measure that represents the proportion of the variance for a dependent variable that's explained by an independent variable or variables in a regression model which is .456 representing 45.6% from Vision 2020 Umurenge Program. This means that remaining 54.4% of socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District come from other variables which are not included in this Model of the research. Adjusted R-squared is a modified version of R-squared that has been adjusted for the number of predictors in the model. The adjusted R-squared increases when the new term improves the model more than would be expected by chance. It decreases when a predictor improves the model by less than expected where it is used to compensate for additional variables in the model where in this case, the adjusted R-square is also 44.2%.

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	515.425	3	171.808	32.393	.000 ^b
	Residual	615.241	116	5.304		
	Total	1130.667	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), VUP financial services, VUP Direct Support, VUP Public works

ANOVA helps to find out whether the differences between groups of data are statistically significant. It works by analyzing the levels of variance within the groups through samples taken from each of them where findings in ANOVA Table 3 showed positive fit mode of 32.393 with p-value is .000b which is less than 0.01, set as standard significance level. This means that the researcher rejected null hypothesis (H₀) stated that there are no significant impacts of Vision 2020 Umurenge Program represented by VUP financial services, VUP Direct Support, VUP Public works on socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District; and we have retained the alternative hypothesis (H₁) stated that Vision 2020 Umurenge Program (VUP financial services, VUP Direct Support, VUP Public works) have significant impact on socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. Generally, F-test to determine whether the variability between group means is larger than the variability of the observations within the groups.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	5.206	.988		5.267	.000
	VUP Public works	.407	.105	.425	3.882	.000
	VUP Direct Support	.410	.123	.278	3.320	.001
	VUP financial services	.089	.143	.065	.627	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Development

An unstandardized coefficient represents the amount of change in a dependent variable Y due to a change of 1 unit of independent variable X. Findings indicated on table 4 showed that $Y = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \epsilon$ where Y is dependent variable indicated by socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. $Y = 5.206 + 0.407x_1 + 0.410x_2 + 0.089x_3 + .988$. Findings from linear regression equation analysis showed that socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District will always depend on constant factor of 5.206 regardless of the presence of other impacts. The other variables explain that; every unit change made in VUP Public works; VUP Direct Support; VUP financial services (i.e., x₁, x₂, x₃) will significantly change socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District with 0.407; 0.410; 0.089 with standard error of 0.988 in this model of the study. The research indicates that wages are sometimes used for help with care work, or as contributions to savings groups.

Women's paid work can have a positive impact on family unity and wellbeing, as husbands and children appreciate the additional income, especially in relation to paying for food making Rwanda's Vision 2020 Umurenge programme public works care-responsive and school costs. Women's daily income helps to smooth household consumption, particularly when men's wages are received only once a month. This is in line with other evidence, which suggests that the VUP 'plays a positive role in improving child well-being and

quality of care. These are adults from Ubudehe category 1, women, 16-17 years age and 60 years and older categories and adults without formal education. These are the groups that formal financial service providers would not easily reach and they have a common challenge of poverty. To address the issue of poverty, the government of Rwanda introduced Vision Umurenge Program (VUP).

Conclusion and Recommendations:

VUP Public works has brought positive changes to their life in particular and that of their communities in general, for they are able to pay school fees for their children, besides, increasing their capacity to have health insurance and for their relatives as well as direct support and financial services also. The present researchers, rightly, conclude that overall, the VUP program has enabled the women in the Rusiga Sector to make significant strides in their social-economic spheres and hence, if the aforesaid can be emulated and be adopted by the neighboring sectors and beyond, communities in Rwanda, in general, would have improved their socioeconomic lives to a large scale. Based to the findings, the problem of the study was solved, the research objectives were achieved, research questions were answered, and research hypotheses were verified where null hypotheses were rejected, and alternative hypothesis was retained stated that Vision 2020 Umurenge Program (VUP financial services, VUP direct support, VUP public works) have significant impact on socio-economic development of women beneficiaries in Rusiga Sector, Rulindo District. The present researcher emphasizes that the VUP should strive to improve its efficiency in terms of its payment and public work implementation systems. Ensuring timely and predictable payments to their respective beneficiaries' payment which is critical to the VUP in its efforts of being able to fulfill its social protection objectives.

Besides, the local government should strengthen its monitoring system of the program. Series of trainings conducted for the VUP staff with a view to enhancing their capacity in monitoring and reporting skills. The budget allocated for the Program in Rusiga Sector should also be reviewed to ensure that in the area are freed from the chains of poverty under which they find themselves. Besides, the sector should train its would-be women in entrepreneurship skills, well in advance, on how to plan and implement business enterprises.

The VUP managers in collaboration with the government and policy makers should recognize the fact that once wages are received on time, so that the women will be able to meet their basic needs and hence, help their respective families, apart from facilitating their school-going children. The local government seek partnership with private sector, civil society and other interested parties with whom they can work together with a view to uplifting the social and economic lives of the women in the selected and in expanding the number of activities presently being undertaken the VUP in the area. In the same vein, the study suggests that some respondents who experienced dissatisfaction with selected aspects of the implementation of VUP projects did not report their dissatisfaction or any other related grievances.

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